

Modular programme for Education and Training
EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATOR

M#6 Plan, Reflect and Learn

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For further information on the EduPASS Project please follow the link:

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Six Core Modules of EduPASS for Early Childhood Educators

The following are the proposed six core modules for Early Childhood Educators education and training programmes that were developed as part of the EduPASS Erasmus+ Project. The core modules should be seen as a flexible reference point which require contextual adaptation. Those individuals and/or organisations using the six core modules to develop learning opportunities for Early Childhood Educators should use the knowledge of their specific context to customise the modules to fit their needs, resources and objectives.

Each of the six EduPASS core modules proposed for ECE education and training programmes was developed building on the knowledge and insights, which can be found in the [European Quality Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care \(ECEC\)](#). The ECEC describes the most important the proposal for key principles of a [Quality Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care \(2014\)](#).

The respective module number and order in which the modules are presented in the table below do not indicate that modules must be introduced in this specific order, when implementing an Early Childhood Educator education and training programme. Rather the numbers simply serve as distinct denominators to help identify specific modules in the overall context of the EduPASS ECE education and training programme.

Core Module Overview

No	Module Title	Description
1	Daily Physical Activity and Play	<p>The module teaches the theoretical basis of the concept of holistic development of children, focusing on changes experienced by children aged 3 to 6 years.</p> <p>It emphasizes the importance of physical activity and play in children's overall development and well-being and highlights the benefits of physical activity during childhood, as well as the potential risks of inactivity on overall health. Additionally, recommendations for children's physical activity levels, strategies for implementation, and the development of skills for assessing the recommended daily physical activity level for children are provided.</p> <p>Finally, a theoretical background for developing intervention programs aimed at improving children's daily physical activity levels is presented. It includes practical workshops and the development of skills for designing and implementing programs to enhance children's daily physical activity levels.</p>

2	Principles of Educating Children	<p>This module aims to guarantee the comprehensive development of children through physical education. For this, different learning units, based mainly on the game, will be carried out such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • motor stories • music, dance and movement • energetic games • games with balls • activities that involve balance, development of laterality, coordination and body awareness • manipulative and construction games
3	Inclusive Teaching	<p>The module aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introduce the theoretical foundations of the concept of inclusion. This includes the legal background (e.g., UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and national legislation), the requirements and goals of inclusion, and didactic models, principles, methods, and strategies for inclusive teaching. • provide opportunities to practically apply and reflect about the principles, methods, and resources of inclusive teaching using specific teaching/case scenarios.
4	Fundamental Movement Skills, Play and Motor Skill Assessment	<p>The module aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introduce the theoretical basics of the concept of fundamental movement skills and play and their importance for children. This includes the structure of fundamental movement skills, their role in children’s development, and didactic principles and methods to promote fundamental movement skills and play. • provide guidance on the practical use of the principles, methods, and resources of teaching/promoting fundamental movement skills and play. • introduce both the theoretical knowledge and the practical skills to objectively measure fundamental movement skills of children using motor tests
5	Hands-on Teaching	<p>This module is designed to enhance the practical skills of Early Childhood Educators through direct participation in learning activities. Through a hands-on approach, participants will develop key skills to foster high-quality interactions with children and create an inclusive learning environment.</p> <p>During the module, Early Childhood Educators will engage in interactive exercises and receive immediate feedback, allowing them to directly apply the pedagogical techniques learned to their educational settings. Strategies for observation and documentation, group dynamics management, and conflict resolution will be addressed, all focused on adapting pedagogical practices to the individual and collective needs of children.</p>

6	Plan, Reflect and Learn	<p>The application of teaching skills, observation and effective decision making is essential to fulfil teaching PAMPS for early childhood and is a cross-cutting capability that should be developed in all ECEs at each stage of their development. The ECE plans, evaluates and reflects each practice and event seeking improvements. In addition, this personal evaluation and reflection underpin a process of ongoing learning and professional development. An important element of this process is the ECE's efforts to with other ECEs in the process.</p> <p>Reflection plays a vital role in early childhood settings. It provides continuous professional development, support, and feedback for all members involved and gives ECEs a safe space to discuss challenging experiences and related feelings. It lays the groundwork for ongoing professional development through consistent self-reflection, community support, and emotional awareness. It's critical that educators can manage the feelings that come with stress to support children's development, communicate effectively with co-workers and families, and find job satisfaction.</p> <p>Questioning what learning and development is taking place to make meaning of what has been observed is crucial for ECE. ECE students should be able to describe why the events are significant to the child and to describe why this experience was important for the child involved.</p>
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Core Module Structure

Core Module	Plan, Reflect and Learn
Module Number	6
Core Module Aim	<p>The aim of the core module is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provide prospective ECEs with the knowledge for planning, reflecting • learning from their own teaching practice.
Module Description	<p>The application of teaching skills, observation and effective decision making is essential to fulfil teaching PAMPS for early childhood and is a cross-cutting capability that should be developed in all ECEs at each stage of their development. The ECE plans, evaluates and reflects each practice and event seeking improvements. In addition, this personal evaluation and reflection underpin a process of ongoing learning and professional development. An important element of this process is the ECE's efforts to with other ECEs in the process.</p> <p>Reflection plays a vital role in early childhood settings. It provides continuous professional development, support, and feedback for all members involved and gives ECEs a safe space to discuss challenging experiences and related feelings. It lays the groundwork for ongoing professional development through consistent self-reflection, community support, and emotional awareness. It's critical that educators can manage the feelings that come with stress to support children's development, communicate effectively with co-workers and families, and find job satisfaction.</p> <p>Questioning what learning and development is taking place to make meaning of what has been observed is crucial for ECE. ECE students should be able to describe why the events are significant to the child and to describe why this experience was important for the child involved.</p>
Module Duration	30 hours
Facilities and Equipment	Seminar room and gym
Methodology	<p>Class based and field-based presentations, during which ECEs will be involved in experiencing practical teaching skills (plan, organize, observe, demonstrate, analyze, provide feedback, evaluate), and creating an environment with reflection, empathy, understanding, support, and personal and professional growth.</p> <p>Self-directed learning and the completion and presentation of case studies will also be included.</p>
Coaching Materials	Logbook / reflection book

<p>Suggested Readings</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Quality Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care • Arthur, L., Beecher, B., Death, E., Dockett, S., Dockett, S., Farmer, S. (2014). Programming and Planning in Early Childhood Settings. Australia: Cengage Learning Australia. • Villareale, C. (2009). Learning from the Children: Reflecting on Teaching. USA: Redleaf Press. • Hayes, C., Daly, J., Duncan, M., Gill, R., Whitehouse, A. (2017). Developing as a Reflective Early Years Professional: A Thematic Approach. (n.p.): Critical Publishing. • Beach, P. S., Reid, G., Collier, D. H. (2017). Motor Learning and Development. Estados Unidos: Human Kinetics. • Smith, Z., Carter, A., Fletcher, T., & Ní Chróinínd, D. (2023). What is important? How one early childhood teacher prioritised meaningful experiences for children in physical education. Journal of Early Childhood Education Research Volume 12, Issue 1,126–149 • Chan, A., & Perkins, M. (2015). Self-review processes: Using critical discourse analysis to improve practices in early childhood education settings. <i>Early Childhood Folio</i>, 19(2), 24–29. doi:10.18296/ecf.0013 	
<p>Evaluation</p>	<p>EduPASS Evaluation Tool for Early Childhood Educator Programmes</p>	
<p>Module structure (each module requires AT LEAST 2 courses)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course 6.1: Planning and Implementing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 4 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 3 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 6.2: Reflecting and Evaluating from Practice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 4 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 3 h Self-Directed Working hours • Course 6.3: Analysis Learning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 4 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 3 h Self-Directed Working hours 	
<p>Learning outcomes for Early Childhood Educators</p>	<p>The module will enable the Early Childhood Educator in training to build the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values) which serve as a foundation when engaging with the children they teach:</p> <p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Childrens’ needs • Pedagogical knowledge • Child development • Understanding individual differences • Assessing methods in ECE 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication skills • Providing a positive learning environment • Conflict resolution • Motivating children • Observation skills • Organisational and planning skills • Importance of being a good listener
	<p>Attitudes: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of</i></p>	<p>Values: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the</i></p>

	<p><i>the following attitudes when engaging with children they teach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive attitude • Respect • Empathy • Valuing individual differences • Cooperation • Professional ethics 	<p><i>following values when engaging with children they teach:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Responsibility • Self-criticism • Positive relationships
<p>Learning outcomes <i>for children/learners</i></p>	<p>The module will enable the Early Childhood Educator in training to support the children they teach to develop the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values):</p>	
	<p>Knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness about their interests and needs • Fundamentals of social interaction • Benefits of play & exploration • Activities in PAMPS 	<p>Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication skills • Cooperation skills • Motivation skills • Active Listening skills
	<p>Attitudes:</p> <p><i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respecting other children’s needs and interests • Enthusiasm • Creativity • Cooperation • Empathy • Patience 	<p>Values:</p> <p><i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respect • Fair play • Empathy • Inclusion
<p>Connection to other Core Module</p>	<p>Module 6 connects to all other Modules 1-5. Throughout all these modules we deem it essential for instructors and learners to implement a “Plan, Reflect, Learn” approach. To highlight this critical skill and provide specific ideas how to engage with and improve in it, we have drafted these module and course descriptions for Module 6.</p>	

Course Structure

Course Title	Planning and Implementing		
Course Number	6.1		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>ECE trainees should be able to see the importance of an adequate planning in early childhood settings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For organization within the setting, to ensure that they know what they are doing and have the appropriate resources available. • To make their work visible to colleagues, families, and other professionals. • To be able to discuss clearly what they are doing, as well as how and why, with parents and other professionals. • To make sure they are developing a wide range of experiences for children through a variety of opportunities, both indoors and outdoors. • To enable them to respond to each child as an individual, by reflecting on what they know about the children and what they identify for their teaching through documentation. • To promote learning and development by supporting children’s individual strengths and abilities as well as those of the group. • To ensure they are maintaining appropriate challenges and stimulation for the children and supporting their active learning, while enabling them to experience success and achievement. • To introduce new ideas and experiences. • To help support any interests and strengths in children’s experiences and learning. 		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / W	3 h	Teaching Unit 1: Planning
	L / W	4 h	Teaching Unit 2: Implementing
	SDL	3 h	Teaching Unit 3: Readings and portfolio of own teaching experiences
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why, what and when plan? • Analysis of examples of planning in ECE • Workshop on planning in ECE settings 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criteria for Implementing • Practical Experience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Implement the own planning ○ Workshop (peer teaching) 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reading: Smith, Z., Carter, A., Fletcher, T., & Ní Chróinínd, D. (2023). What is important? How one early childhood teacher prioritised meaningful experiences for children in 	

		<p>physical education. Journal of Early Childhood Education Research Volume 12, Issue 1,126–149</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Portfolio of own teaching experiences (peer teaching)
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Course Title	Reflecting and Evaluating from Practice		
Course Number	6.2		
Course Description / Main Objective	Reflect – evaluating the effectiveness of the plan		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	W / PE	3 h	Teaching Unit 1: Observing and collecting information
	W / PE	4 h	Teaching Unit 2: Reflecting on collected information
	SDL	3 h	Teaching Unit 3: Readings and portfolio of own teaching experiences
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategies for observing in ECE settings • Analysis of observations 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What information is valuable? • Analysis of peer teaching (experience) 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reading: Villareale, C. (2009). Learning from the Children: Reflecting on Teaching. USA: Redleaf Press. • Portfolio on reflecting and learning from own teaching experiences 	

Course Title	Analysis Learning		
Course Number	6.3		
Course Description / Main Objective	<p>Questioning what learning and development is taking place to make meaning of what has been observed is crucial for ECE. ECE students should be able to describe why the events are significant to the child and to describe why this experience was important for the child involved.</p> <p>When making an analysis of their observation the ECEs should be able to ask themselves the following questions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What learning took place here? 2. What strengths and interests can I identify from the observation? 3. Is there anything in the observation that concerns you from a developmental perspective? What can I do to support the child's learning in this area? Who do I need to speak to about this? 4. How could I further support and extend this child's interest/strength/learning journey? 5. Is this learning observation significant – can I plan future experiences from this observation? 		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L / W	3 h	Teaching Unit 1: Self-review process
	L / W	4 h	Teaching Unit 2: Analysis learning
	SDL	3 h	Teaching Unit 3: Readings and portfolio of own teaching experiences
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-review guidelines • Workshop on self-review techniques • Analysis of peer self-reviews 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning needs analysis: step-by-step process • How to create a culture of leaning in ECE context (workshop) 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reading: Chan, A., & Perkins, M. (2015). Self-review processes: Using critical discourse analysis to improve practices in early childhood education settings. <i>Early Childhood Folio</i>, 19(2), 24–29. doi:10.18296/ecf.0013 • Continue portfolio on self-review from own teaching experiences 	